

Fifty Years After the INA-Casa Plan

The quote Plan to Increase Blue-collar Employment. Housing for Workers”, better known as the Ina-Casa Plan was approved in Italy fifty years ago. It was the first substantial attempt to build public housing throughout the country and represented one of the most important phases of post-WWII reconstruction, as well as, more generally, the history of twentieth-century architecture and urban planning. The time has now come to reflect on the importance - both nationally and locally - of this patrimony of housing and on the urban space it created in Italian cities.

A brief history is necessary. The Ina-Casa Plan was promoted by the Minister of Labor in 1949, a few years after the war, with the goal of resolving the problem of the blue-collar unemployment. At that time building seemed to be the sector best-suited to solving this problem and to re-launching post-war economic development.

The Plan was financed with a system, then proposed as an expression of national solidarity, that foresaw the participation of the State, employers and, to a small extent, all employees. It proved to be an important experience not only from the point of view of employment. Over a period of fourteen years, from 1949 to 1963, it permitted the construction of about 400.000 residences (two million rooms), allowing thousands of families residing in poor conditions (often in basements, caves and hovels) to move into healthy, decent housing. The strategy for locating projects favored their maximum dispersion and new neighborhoods were built in all major Italian cities, along with complexes or even individual buildings in most of the smaller centers. Access to housing ownership was widely favored, and under pressure by Christian Democratic Party then in power almost 70% of the residences built were conceded on a mortgage basis.

The projects were planned and coordinated by a lean centralized structure, made up of a political

branch, known as the Implementation Committee and directed by the Torinese engineer Filiberto Guala, and a technical branch or Ina-Casa Management, presided over by Arnaldo Foschini, an outstanding exponent of the “Rome school”, and then head of the Faculty of Architecture at the University of Rome. Foschini’s role was determinant, both from the point of view of the Plan’s operation and its technical contents, and from that of having involved the entire category of architects on a national level.

It was not only the “best” Italian architects - Mario Ridolfi, Giancarlo De Carlo, Mario De Renzi, Mollino, Ludovico Quaroni, Giuseppe Samonà, Federico Gorio, Gino Valle ... -, who worked for Ina-Casa but almost all the architects of that time. Competitions were held on specific design topics, from which the lists of suitable designers were selected. Over time the architects and engineers who worked on Ina-Casa projects grew to be numbered in the thousands. For some middle-aged architects Ina-Casa commissions were the first opportunities of a certain importance after the war, while for younger professionals they provided first jobs. It can perhaps be affirmed that the Ina-Casa Plan represented not only an opportunity for broadening architects and urban planners’ thought but for their employment as well, alongside that of blue-collar workers.

One of the salient aspects of these fourteen years was the construction of housing within morphologically and functionally designed and completed wholes, that is, entire neighborhoods. It was the first, significant, ample and widespread Italian experience of this sort. The Plan was seen, above all by Italian architects and urban planners, as a great opportunity for correcting the aim of post-war reconstruction: no more casual dissemination of projects, incapable of imparting order and design quality to expanding Italian cities, but a policy that called for “grouping” projects together and constructing the city in organic and self-sufficient sections.

Some of the neighborhoods that were built went down in the history of Italian post-war architecture and were articulated around varied concepts of the city, space and community [i.e.: Tiburtino in Rome by Ridolfi and Quaroni, Falchera in Turin by Astengo, Forte Quezzi in Genoa by Daneri, Cavedone in Bologna by Gorio, Cesate by Albini, Gardella, Barbiano by Belgioioso, Peressutti and Rogers, San Marco in Mestre by Samonà and Piccinato, Valco San Paolo in Rome by De Renzi and Muratori, the Sesto San Giovanni project by De Carlo, Cerignola by Ridolfi, etc). But it is not only the “exemplary examples” that are worthy of note. Whoever visits these neighborhoods today can note the effort that was made to elevate and promote the quality of architectural and urban design, something Ina-Casa in-

deed achieved. In this sense, the entity's architectural office, coordinated until 1952 by Adalberto Libera, kept an important check on projects and published a few brief manuals drafted with the goal of "guiding", instead of codifying, housing and neighborhood design, in the attempt to attribute a shared quality to all projects, while at the same time avoiding excessive homogeneity and repetition in implementing the plan.

With the Ina-Casa plan an attempt was made to delineate an Italian route to modernization capable of bringing innovation and tradition together. The plan actually revealed the aspiration of achieving progress in technique, life styles, and an idea of the city that was capable of upholding Italian and local tradition. The manuals' recommended paying attention to the characteristics of the landscape and the preexisting historical centers, to life styles, the climate, construction materials, artisan products, local building systems, etc., demonstrating the idea of rooting the new projects in a place and tradition that was regional as well as national. (i.e.: Capri, Alberobello, Perugia, Cortina).

In addition to giving attention to local specifics, the manuals also suggested looking toward foreign models and were rich in European references. The examples cited included those of Northern Europe, the garden cities or the neighborhoods of Scandinavian organicism, rather than rationalist neighborhoods. The second manual explained: "Housing has to contribute to forming the urban environment, keeping in mind the spiritual and material needs of real men and not abstract beings: of men that don't love and don't understand indefinite and monotone repetitions of the same type of residence... that don't love checkerboard arrangements, but environments that are quiet and animated at the same time. It was to be the site conditions, the sunlight, the landscape, the vegetation, the preexisting environment, the sense of color that were to suggest the composition of the layout so that inhabitants of the new urban nuclei could have the impression that there was something spontaneous, genuine and inseparably melded with the place in which they rose".

In support of these ideas, an articulation, differentiation and hierarchy of elements were recommended in the urban composition: building types, open spaces, street layouts, centrality, services, etc.. All of these elements were important in expressing the organic and community approach to the city that was widespread in urban theory and design in the first half of the fifties in Italy and that Ina-Casa contributed to exploring.

Despite its importance, no one in the past decades has written either a comprehensive history of this national plan or a set of local case studies. All one finds on the Ina-Casa Plan are a few partial

and fragmented texts within other more comprehensive history books on building policies and architecture or urban planning of the second half of the twentieth century, all written from a particular point of view or orientation. In both the literature and in common opinion this plan has often been covered by a thin blanket of criticism, at times much too banal and commonplace. [The neighborhoods of Ina-Casa Plan are dismissed as projects leading to unchecked urban expansion, producers of urban revenue, creators of marginalization for the weaker social classes, expressions of a vernacular idea of living and of architecture. The Plan is seen as overbearing in the face of local administration, an expression of conservative politics, etc..] Nor has attention been given in more recent years to the projects for up-grading, protecting and conserving the neighborhoods built at that time.

An occasion to look back on this was presented last year in Venice, where I organized a series initiatives focused on this Plan, including an exhibition and a conference, as well as a design competition for young architects to rehabilitate three of these neighborhoods. The goal behind my research is not only that reconstructing a period of Italian architectural and urban planning history, bringing it once again to the center of architects, urban planners and scholars' attention, but above all to work on the material results of this plan, to re-view at a distance of some decades the neighborhoods built in various urban spaces, to be able to pinpoint their place and meaning not only in the history of twentieth-century Italian architecture and urban planning, but in the contemporary city and society as well.

Returning more generally to that experience of housing and urban space, to the neighborhoods constructed at that time, as well as how they have fared over time and how we as citizens, scholars, designers find them today, can be justified in terms of *interest* and *dissatisfaction*.

The *interest* is for the "public city", for those neighborhoods built in 1900s by various entities and administrations, particularly after WWII, with the goal of providing housing and services to weaker social classes. Going beyond the specific national and local cases as well as the architectural quality of some of its sections, the public city as a whole is surely of interest. It is interpretable not only as a place of emargination and decay, but also as a "document/monument" of modernity, the result of social policies, and ideas about the city and society that have contributed to creating modern urban planning.

851 Ever since the nineteenth century urban planning has pursued goals of common interests and has created theories and tools that have attempted to shift the confines between two processes: that of con-

structuring public space and that of building its private equivalent. It has tried to bring individual and collective interests together in a "fair" way, taking the position of those social groups less favored by the market, by institutions and by history. It has elaborated methods and tools to recognize and satisfy primary, essential, "natural" needs, with respect to which it deems it to be "fair", of priority and general interest, that collectivity, and thus the institutions that represent it, respond. Thus, urban planning has proposed itself as a broad "representation" of man's fundamental needs, i.e. inhabitable space; of those needs that concern entire social groups and cannot be met by individuals and the private sphere alone, but necessitate public intervention capable of legitimizing their general character.

These fundamental presuppositions, which organized modern urban planning research and the modern movement, also led to ideas on the city and its space, on neighborhoods and housing, and on domestic and urban space that were pursued and most explicitly expressed in the neighborhoods built for public housing. In Italy as well - and on the example of other countries - this kind of response (even if often quantitatively insufficient) produced new urban areas. The neighborhoods built by Ina-Casa in the 1950s number among these.

Public housing took on additional value in that it became an important material with which to compose the space of the twentieth-century city, with which to give it new form. Entire areas of the city were designed and built in an attempt to oppose the urban outskirts then developing, especially after WWII, through the juxtaposition of dispersed, banal, fragmentary and speculative projects, in the attempt to point out new directions for the city's growth and to propose examples that could be imitated by private intervention. These neighborhoods became the symbol of spatial conquest; of the endowment of uses and primary facilities; and of the coexistence of individual and collective spheres, of built and open space, and of interior and exterior inhabitable space.

The public neighborhoods reveal traces of those research programs that, since the last century, have demonstrated how what truly takes on weight and value in the city, even with respect to housing, is open space. Here the project of modernity that dedicated so much attention to unbuilt space appears more limpid: here open and built space belong reciprocally to one another; each one attributes form, meaning and value to the other. The size and characteristics of the site are able to dictate conditions to the built environment: the building type - the minimum unit of the urban composition -, its measure, form and repetition are conditioned on one hand

by the study of the housing module and on the other by the amount and conformation of the unbuilt land.

To the *interest* for the public city, understood as representative of the issues above, we can add the *dissatisfaction* that, through the generically critical judgements superimposed on it in Italy as elsewhere, has come to the point of making it indistinctly synonymous with emargination, urban and social decay. The neighborhoods, especially those constructed from the 1960s on, have become emblematic of the poor quality of the urban outskirts. Even the term outskirts itself is almost always associated with negative meanings and hence the entire city of this century has become indistinctly problematic. The dissatisfaction is for the commonplace; for the criticism one finds deposited on the space of our city, a dust that inhibits new approaches and reinterpretations capable of identifying the best sections of the modern city and not only those that fill the history books of architecture and urban planning.

The problematic nature of the criticism on the public city and the outskirts also derives from the fact that they involve, perhaps unconsciously but certainly deductively, a large part of twentieth-century urban history and those studies aimed at improving inhabitable space which began to be developed in the nineteenth century and were later taken on by modern movement. Yet, by avoiding generic and undifferentiated criticism a more comprehensive balance can be reached, an assessment capable of acknowledging that without this research and these neighborhoods it would have been impossible to satisfy the housing and service demand of millions of Europeans. And without these experiments city space would be much less articulated and rich, and the history of urban planning and architecture much less intense and fertile. All of this contributes to the value of the public neighborhoods built throughout the century, which today, at least in Italy, no longer represent a modality of the city's construction and growth. This, in turn, obliges us to question ourselves not only on the issue of rehabilitation but also that of how to protect this modern patrimony.

Coming back to public neighborhoods and in particular to those of Ina-Casa, it is necessary to recognize the traces of the previously mentioned research not only by measuring dissatisfaction with facile criticism and prejudice, not only by ascertaining the interest for some of these architectural structures and spaces, but at times by observing their decay as well and by recognizing their need for transformation, ascertaining the all-to-frequent inappropriateness of new maintenance projects (often left to single initiatives), or that of rehabilitation projects promoted by public entities insensitive to protection.

The issue of up-grading and protecting these neighborhoods is not a simple one. It is even more problematic with respect to the conservation of modern buildings, given the particular nature of these sections of the city which are not individual structures but urban complexes, the results of articulating different kinds of space and use. They are indeed sections of the contemporary city and society whose inhabitants express a demand for quality that requires renovation projects that can contrast with protective acts, when understood as simple conservation.

To be able to launch effective projects of up-grading, rehabilitation and protection (listed in a sequential order), it is necessary to ask a few more general questions. In the first place, what does "patrimony" mean for the public city and, therefore, what should be protected? What has been constructed, the buildings, the collective facilities, the materials, the open spaces, etc.? The original design concept, often modified or betrayed in construction; the layout and the design of the neighborhood as a whole, the single principles of settlement, etc.? The idea of community it attempted to express? The forms the neighborhood has taken on through the modifications brought about by its inhabitants' day-to-day? The traces left behind by the people who have lived there and changed it?

What has patrimony become and for whom? For the inhabitants, administrators, urban planners and architects? As a consequence, how should rehabilitation-protection projects and actions be articulated and dosed? What are the most suitable tools? How should we put together tools and cognitive methods for identifying and cataloguing these ambits of protection and how are they to be placed in relation to descriptive processes and projects of intervention?

And then, in the specific Italian case of the neighborhoods produced by the Ina-Casa Plan, are they to be considered as a group of patrimonial subjects for which to define policies for intervention and protection coordinated on a national level? Should the great variety of projects built (of which a census must be taken, how many and where?) be considered as a set of distinct blocks, at the same time belonging to a single unitary constellation, representing the result of the same plan, implemented in a circumscribed period? In this sense what would constitute the minimum common denominator to be identified as the basis for a unitary national policy of protection? Or, on the contrary, should rehabilitation and protection policies be defined locally, given that each neighborhood belongs much more to a local urban and social history than to other more comprehensive histories?

Amidst many doubts and questions, one certainty can be affirmed. In light of all the above, what lends itself most to being redefined and re-signified is the unbuilt public and collective space and the set of relationships it establishes with built space and with the individuals and the social groups living in it. What, from the design phase on, has distinguished these neighborhoods as unitary urban sections and differentiates them from the other neighboring twentieth-century urban expansion is the role of open space in the design of the whole. From the very idea of residential unit itself, this space carried out - in design phase and "on the ground" - a role in structuring the entire area. It is declined here in a broader concept of "inhabitable space" in which the solid and the void, the interior and the exterior, the domestic and the urban are interconnected. In the passage from planning to implementation there is often a schism between the construction of the buildings and that of its open space and, over time, between the maintenance of the former and the care for the latter. These separations have had a negative impact on the quality on the unbuilt environment, which has at times remained vague, disqualified, ruled by cars and expropriated by the inhabitants.

Redefining this space - perhaps the only element that can establish new relationships between urban areas and people - renders particularly important public intervention in the heterogeneous landscape of the contemporary city, where the absence of meaningful relationships between things estranges social subjects and their activities. After many years of introducing new ideas about living and physical representation in urban space, public intervention has now to confront the importance of this space's "meaning".

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A Falchera

Torino, Falchera Area, 1950-52, G. Astengo (u), S. Molli Boffa, M. Passanti (c), N. Renacco, A. Rizzotti; E.G. Sottsass (c), G. Becker, G. Fasana, N. Grassi, M. Oreglia, P. Perona, A. Romano.

Fig. A1 - General Plan

Fig. A3 - Central Square

Fig. A2 – Aerial View

Fig. A4 – Central Square

Fig. A5 – Historical Photos

Fig. A6 – Historical Photos

Fig. A7 – Historical Photos

Fig. A8 – Historical Photos

B Genova

Genova, Forte Quezzi Area, 1956-1957, L.C. Daneri (c), L. Grossi Bianchi, V. Oddi, F. Surace, G. Zappa; E. Fuselli (c), R. De Maestri, G. Fortunato, G. Gaggero, M. Innocenti; C. Andreani (c), G. Caioli, D. Corte, O. Matelli, M. Tavoletti, P. Tessiore; R. Morozzo Della Rocca (c), M. Braccialini, G. Cotroneo, M. Dasso, D. Datta, A. Spina; M. Pateri (c), V. Ghiglione, E. Loi, M. Loi, M. Testoni; G.F. Pulitzer (c), E. Arnaldi, A. Guerello, G. Pazzi; A. Sibilla (c), E. Magnani, A. Sibilla, V. Esposti

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2-3-4-5 Historical Photos

6-7 Drafts of the Church

Fig. 1B – General Plan

Fig. 2B – Historical Photos

Fig. 3B – Historical Photos

Fig. 4B – Historical Photos

Fig. 5B – Historical Photos

Fig. 6B – Drafts of the Church

Fig. 7B – Drafts of the Church

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